

The Sacred Spaces of the Ajivika Monks: Barabar and Nagarjuni Caves

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Abstract:

The ancient Indian religious and philosophical spectrum went far beyond Hinduism, Jainism and Buddhism to include sects that often challenged the popular dictates. Of these, were the Ajivikas who believed in the idea of *Niyati* – a central tenet that formed the base of all actions and negated human choices and intentions. In their pursuance of strong determinism, the Ajivikas were often labeled as heretics by the opposing, contemporaneous faiths. Their brief existence is marked with instances of rivalry, co-existence and challenges.

Over the years, the tradition has perished leaving behind some tangible remains in the form of rock-cut architectures. In the absence of any direct textual evidence, the information that these architectural remains encapsulate form a strong ground for scholars to rely on. Seven caves excavated in the Barabar and Nagarjuni hills have been dated to the reign of Emperor Asoka and his successors. Inscriptional data found inside these caves have been ascribed to Emperor Asoka and his descendants and record the donation of cave shelters to the Ajivika monks.

These monuments marked the beginning of rock-cut architecture in India that later took up more developed patterns and forms. The article proposes to analyze the nature and form of the

rock-cut caverns. These architectural remains throw considerable light on the religious affiliations of the time.

Keywords: Ajivikas, Rock-cut caves, Barabar, Nagarjuni, Asoka, Maurya

Prelude :

In the backdrop of a dynamic milieu, the Ajivikas emerged as a nonconformist group alongside Buddhism and Jainism. The doctrine, which emerged between the fourth and second centuries BCE, shared a common belief with other contemporaneous heretical groups – they rejected the idea of polytheism and monism as was prevalent around that time. Instead, they underlined the importance of the rule of natural law in the universe. Of the three systems, the doctrine of *Niyati* – a central tenet of the Ajivikas that propounded belief in fate and ineffectuality of human needs, justly highlighted the vision. (Basham, 1951)

Unlike Buddhism and Jainism, the tradition of Ajivikism, has left behind very little evidence that may not be sufficient to construct a whole image. No texts or documents can be reliably identified to have been composed by the members or by those closely linked to the sect (Balcerowicz, 2022). Textual references in Pali, Prakrit and Sanskrit have unanimously labelled the Ajivikas as determinists. Basham in *History and Doctrines of the Ajivikas* has also reiterated this statement based on his study of the texts. In the absence of any direct material, the idea of the Ajivikas has been heavily drawn from Buddhist, Jain and Brahmin sources. Therefore, Benimadhab Barua opined, all sources must be thoroughly investigated to unearth the truth (Kashyap, 2023).

The dearth of authentic textual references has posed a serious challenge in the construction of a reliable narrative. Scholars like A.L. Basham, Benimadhab Barua, have produced seminal works in this arena by focusing their studies on a huge corpus of references. Their findings have been of immense significance in our understanding of the sect and its doctrines. In addition to these studies, what remains are a group of caves in the eastern zone of

India that serve as the earliest surviving religious edifices in India. These monuments, which served as shelter to the wandering monks, are crucial tangible evidence. Though these do not contain any data that can help further our understanding of the sect, they are a true testament to the position that the Ajivikas held during the time and the religious setup. These remains have been widely studied as markers of brilliant workmanship and architectural planning. Focusing on this aspect, the paper proposes to conduct a thorough study and detailed analysis of the rock-cut caverns. The data unearthed will help uncover information about the religious structure of the time. The paper, however, does not deal with the doctrinal aspect of Ajivikism. It presents a study of the religious edifices related to the sect with the help of archaeological and historical records.

Methodology:

The proposed paper would require a critical analysis of archaeological remains as well as thorough examination of historical records and recent scholarships. The collective findings will present a comprehensive narrative to further our understanding of the proposed topic. By sifting through the archaeological and written sources, the article intends to underline the importance of the Barabar and Nagarjuni caves in the spectrum of Indian religious architecture, to thoroughly examine the architectural setup and planning, to interpret inscriptional records and to discuss the amalgamation of religion and politics of the time by focusing on areas such as royal patronage.

Significance of the Site:

The twin hills of Barabar and Nagarjuni are located in a deserted range of granite hills near Gaya in Bihar. The hills accommodate a group of seven caves that mark the earliest tradition of rock-cut architecture in India. Dating back to the reign of the Mauryan Empire (c.325 BCE – 185 BCE), the caverns reflect the religious attitudes of its rulers Emperor Asoka and subsequently his grandson, Dasaratha. The four caves situated in the Barabar hills are – Lomas Rishi cave, Sudama cave, Karna Chaupar cave, Viswakarma cave. Of these the Sudama, Karna Chaupar and Viswakarma caves contain inscriptions in the Prakrit language and Brahmi script

that mention Asoka as *Priyadarshin*. The Lomas Rishi cave, which Huntington refers to as “*the most interesting from the artistic point of view*”, does not bear a Mauryan inscription. However, based on its association with the other three caverns and similarities in form, Huntington ascribes it to the Asokan period (Huntington, 2014). The Nagarjuni hills house three caves – Vadathi-ka-Kubha, Vapiya-ka-Kubha and Gopi-ka-Kubha - that have been linked to Dasaratha based on inscriptional records. These inscriptions, too, are composed in the Prakrit language and Brahmi script (Sircar, 1942).

Besides being an architectural landmark, the caverns shed considerable light on the various facets of the changing setup of the Indo-Gangetic valley - recurrent political, religious and social contests. Emperor Asoka’s relation with the Ajivikas remains a debated issue. The *Asokavadana* mentions an incident that enraged the Emperor. It states, “*A follower of the Nirgrantha (Mahavira) painted a picture, showing Buddha prostrating Himself at the feet of Nirgrantha. Asoka ordered all the Ajivikas of Purnavardhana (North Bengal) to be killed. In one day, eighteen thousand Ajivikas lost their lives.*” Mukhopadhyaya states that the author may have confused the Nirgranthas with the Ajivikas (Mukhopadhyaya, 1963). Basham opined that the use of the terms Nirgranthas and Ajivikas makes it difficult to ascertain the intention of the event – if it was intended for the Jainas or the Ajivikas (Basham, 1951).

This account of mass persecution has led several scholars to question Asoka’s equation with the sect. However, the tangible remains found in Bihar puts forth an extremely pertinent question – If Asoka and his policies were hostile towards the Ajivikas, why did the Emperor take the effort to donate caverns for sheltering the wandering monks? Basham argued that Asoka’s donation of the hermitages is indicative of his support of the sect and the influence it wielded in Magadha at the time (Basham, 1951). Asoka’s policy of inclusion and tolerance may have also played a part in this initiative. There is, however, some uncertainty regarding the donor of the caves. This aspect will be dealt with later in the paper.

Barabar Caves: Karna Chaupar, Viswakarma, Sudama, Lomas Rishi:

Forster in *A Passage To India* presents a lucid account of the caverns which he renamed as “Marabar”. He states that the caves are similar in plan – a tunnel (eight feet long, five feet high and three feet wide) leading to a circular chamber (twenty feet in diameter). In the absence of much light, the caves appear dark. While the circular chamber is highly polished, the walls of the tunnel are left rough (Forster, 2022).

Barabar and Nagarjuni hill cave inscriptions. Photo credit – Wikimedia Commons. Author – Eugen Hultsch and Alexander Cunningham

Karna Chaupar:

Karna Chaupar is located on the northern side of the Barabar hill. It consists of a single chamber with vaulted roof and polished surface. At one end, there is a long, rectangular rock-cut slab. The entrance has sloping jamb. It contains an inscription dated to the 19th year of consecration of Emperor Asoka. The translation of the inscription proposed by E. Hultzsch reads as –

“When king Priyadarsin had been anointed nineteen years, this cave in the very pleasant Kha[latika mountain] was given by me for (shelter during) the rainy season.” (Hultzsch, 1925)

1 lāja Piyadasī ekunavi-
2 sati-vasā[bh]isi[t]e ja[lagh]o-
3 [sāgama]thāta [me] i[yaṁ kubhā]
4 su[p]i[y]e Kha¹ [di]-
5 nā²

Karna Chaupar inscription. Source – *CORPUS INSCRIPTIONUM INDICARUM*, E. Hultzsch

This reading proposed by E. Hultzsch does neither clearly specify the Emperor’s donation nor mentions the Ajivikas. The author admits that the caves may have been given by another member of the imperial family. If the mention of *Priyadasī* in the inscription does not refer to Asoka, it may then point towards other members like Chandragupta, Bindusara or the successors of Dasaratha. The inscriptions found in the Nagarjuni hill caves specify the name of Dasaratha. Hence, had he been the donor of Barabar caverns, he would have mentioned his name. Basham opined that no other ruler has a stronger probability than Asoka to be the donor. The tradition of inscribing rock was not known before Asoka and later successors have not left behind any epigraphic material (Basham, 1951).

Hultzsch mentions that the end of the inscription is marked by a *swastika*, a dagger and a fish below them. The presence of these symbols that are considered auspicious in Buddhism, has led some to believe that the cave was a gift to the Buddhist monks as shelter during the rainy season.

However, later scholars like Henry Falk have re-analysed and interpreted the translation that brought to light new material. His reading clearly specifies the donation of the caves to the Ajivikas.

*lāja piyadasī ekunavī
sati-vaśābhisite jalūṭhaṃ
āgamithā tata iyaṃ kubhā
su[p]i[y]ekha (ājivikehi) [di]
nā*

Harry Falk's interpretation of Karna Chaupar inscription. Source -*The Diverse Degrees of Authenticity of Asokan Texts*

"When king Priyadarsin had been anointed nineteen years, he went to Jalutha and then this cave (called) Supriyeksa was given to the Ajivikas." (Falk, 2009)

The entrance hall also has an inscription that reads "*Daridra Kantara*" ("The mendicant's cave"). The inscription is probably a later addition, post-dating the Mauryan Empire.

Volume representation of Karna Chaupar cave

Photo credit – Wikipedia, Author – Percy Brown

Entrance of the Karna Chaupar cave

Photo credit – Wikimedia Commons, Author – Thomas Fraser Peppe

“*Daridra Kantara*” – near the entrance of Karna Chaupar Cave

Photo credit – Wikimedia Commons, Author – Devajyoti Sarkar

Viswakarma Cave:

The Viswakarma cave consists of an outer chamber with highly polished walls and a flat roof and an unfinished circular inner chamber. The way to the circular chamber from the outer room is through another quadrilateral-shaped space. The cave contains an inscription that can be dated to the twelfth year of consecration of Asoka.

- 1 lājinā Piyadasinā duvā-
- 2 ḍasa-vasābhisitenā iyam
- 3 kubhā Khalatika-pavatasi
- 4 dinā [ājivi]kehi *

Viswakarma cave inscription. Source – *CORPUS INSCRIPTIONUM INDICARUM*, E. Hultzsch

“By king Priyadarsin (when he had been) anointed twelve years, this cave in the Khalatika mountain was given to the Ajivikas” (Hultzsch, 1927).

Volume representation of Viswakarma cave

Photo credit – Wikipedia, Author – Percy Brown

Entrance of the Viswakarma cave

Photo credit – Wikipedia

Sudama Cave:

Located on the southern side, the Sudama cave lies close to Lomas Rishi cave. The cave consists of two chambers – the roughly inner circular chamber with a hemispherical vaulted roof and a long rectangular chamber with an arched ceiling. The inside has a smooth finish and is marked by the characteristic Mauryan polish creating a mirror effect. It also contains an inscription ascribed to the twelfth year of consecration of Asoka.

- 1 **lājinā Piyadasinā duvāḍasa-[vasābhisitenā]¹**
- 2 **[iyaṃ Nigoha]-kubhā¹ di[nā ājivikehi]¹**

Sudama Cave inscription. Source – *CORPUS INSCRIPTIONUM INDICARUM*, E. Hultzsch

“By king Priyadarsin, (when he had been) anointed twelve years, this Banyan cave was given to the Ajivikas” (Hultsch, 1927).

Volume representation of Sudama cave

Photo credit – Wikipedia

Sudama cave - the inner circular chamber (to the left) and the rectangular space with an arched ceiling. Photo credit – Rana Safvi and Devajyoti Sarkar

Lomas Rishi Cave:

Except for the treatment of the façade, the Lomas Rishi cave is identical in form to the Sudama cave. The doorway is fashioned after wooden architecture and Huntington argues that the style is strictly Indic in character. The ornate details of the doorway make it evident that ancient India had a long history in wooden craftsmanship (Huntington, 2014).

The ogee-shaped doorway is topped by a finial. The wooden beams have been carefully carved but are only meant for decorative purposes. The pillars supporting the roof are slightly angled. A round arch brings the entire composition together within which a rectangular opening serves as the actual door. Two separate arched bands above the door are elaborately carved. The upper band is carved in latticework imitating wood. The lower band is embellished with a band of elephants in progression with recurring stupa-like emblems. At the end of the architraves there is an image of *makara* (Huntington, 2014).

The interior of the cave consists of a long rectangular hall attached to a circular room resembling a thatched hut. The inside is very similar to that of Sudama cave that unlike Lomas Rishi (which remained incomplete) was nearly completed. The walls would have had a similar Mauryan stonework polish. In regard to this, Huntington argues that the incomplete and rough appearance of the walls was probably a conscious decision on the part of the artisans to replicate woodwork. The walls also bear incision marks that would imitate wood grain. Further examination however shows that the marks were the result of an unfinished project (Huntington, 2014).

The cave contains a six-line inscription written in Sanskrit using the northern class of alphabets. It records the installation of an image of Vishnu in the form of Krishna by the Maukhari chieftain, Anantavarman. The inscription may be dated to the 5th-6th century AD (Sahai, 1983).

Nagarjuni Hills: Gopi-Ka-Kubha, Vapiya-Ka-Kubha and Vadathi-Ka-Kubha

“The Milkmaid’s Cave” or Gopi-Ka-Kubha has a long elliptical hall with finely polished walls. The entrance has sloping jambs. Both the ends are semi-circular. Fergusson and Burgess argue that while the cave seems to resemble a vihara, the space inside is too large for sheltering a hermit and is not divided into cells as is found in the western viharas (Burgess, 1880). The cave contains an inscription that may be dated to c. 215 BCE. The inscription is carved over the doorway and records its donation to the Ajivikas by king Dasaratha (Sahai, 1983).

Another inscription found on the left side of the entrance records the installation of an image of Goddess Parvati as Katyayani in the cave by the Maukhari chieftain, Anantavarman. The inscription is written in Sanskrit using the northern class of alphabets and can be dated to 6th -7th century AD (Sahai, 1983).

The Vapiya-Ka-Kubha or “Well Cave” may have derived its name from a nearby sacred well. A small porch connected to a doorway leads to the principal room. The doorway has a sloping jamb. The ceiling is vaulted and the inside has a high polish. The left side of the porch has a four-line inscription recording the donation of the cave by Dasaratha in the beginning of his rule. The inscription states that the cave was given to the Ajivikas by king Dasaratha in the last quarter of the 3rd century BCE (Sahai, 1983).

To the west of Vapiya-Ka-Kubha lies Vadathi-Ka-Kubha. Placed in a natural opening in the rock, a passageway leads to a rectangular chamber with polished walls. On the right hand jamb of the doorway a similar inscription is found that may be dated to c. 218 BCE.

The Vadathi cave also bears an inscription of a later date (around 6th century AD) that is found on the right side of the entrance. Written in Sanskrit with the northern class of alphabets, the inscription records the installation of an image representing Siva as Bhupati along with his consort, Parvati in the cave. The donation was made by the Maukhari chieftain, Anantavarman (Sahai, 1983).

Hand sketch drawing of the Nagarjuni caves procured from Alexander Cunningham's Archaeological Survey Report, 1861-62. Photo credit - Wikimedia Commons, Author – Ms. Sarah Welch

Gopi-Ka-Kubha. Photo credit – Wikimedia Commons

Vapiya-Ka-Kubha and Vadathi-Ka-Kubha (to the left)

Photo credit - Wikipedia

I

1 वह्निक[र] कुभा दषलथेन देवानंपियेना

2 आनंतलियं अभिषितेना [आजीविकेहि]

3 भदतेहि¹ वाष-निषिदियाये निषिटे

4 आ-चंदम-भूलियं [॥*]

II

1 गोपिका कुभा दषलथेना देवा[न] पि-

2 येना आनंतलियं अभिषितेना आजी-

3 विके[हि] [भद]तेहि वाष-निसिदियाये

4 निसिठा आ-चंदम-भूलियं [॥*]

III

1 वडधिका कुभा दषलथेना देवानं-

2 पियेना आनंतलियं अ[भि]षितेना [आ]-

3 [जी]विकेहि भदतेहि वा[ष-निषि]दियाये

4 निषिठा आ-चंदम-भूलियं [॥*]²

Inscriptions of King Dasaratha found in the Nagarjuni Hills. Source - *SELECT INSCRIPTIONS BEARING ON INDIAN HISTORY AND CIVILIZATION*, D. C. Sircar

I—वह्निका [इति] गुहा दशरथेन देवानांप्रियेण आनन्तर्येण अभिषिक्तेण (=अभिषेकवर्षे) आजीविकेभ्यः [तत्र]भवद्गुह्यः (=महनीयेभ्यः) वर्षा-निषद्यायै (=वर्षा-वासाय) निस्पृष्टा आ-चान्द्रमः-सौर्यम् । II—गोपिका [इति] गुहा दशरथेन देवानांप्रियेण आनन्तर्येण अभिषिक्तेन आजीविकेभ्यः [तत्र]भवद्गुह्यः वर्षा-निषद्यायै निस्पृष्टा आ-चान्द्रमः-सौर्यम् । III—वडधिका [इति] गुहा दशरथेन देवानांप्रियेण आनन्तर्येण अभिषिक्तेन आजीविकेभ्यः [तत्र]भवद्गुह्यः वर्षा-निषद्यायै निस्पृष्टा आ-चान्द्रमः-सौर्यम् ॥

The Sanskrit version of the inscription. Source - *SELECT INSCRIPTIONS BEARING ON INDIAN HISTORY AND CIVILIZATION*, D. C. Sircar

Conclusion:

The data procured from various sources offer a broad understanding of the rock-cut caverns in eastern India. The inscriptional records found inside the caverns provide insight into the concurrent religious scenario and affiliation of the rulers. Their structure and the artistic rendering of the façade point towards skillful workmanship. The highly polished walls with a mirror-like glaze in the interior surfaces of the manually carved, granite caves delineate high precision and mastery. The interior planning indicates that these edifices were not meant for residential purpose but to serve religious and sacred purposes.

The strategic location of the site has been popular among several religious communities like the Buddhists, Hindus and Muslims as is evident from traces of their occupation. The popularity and prosperity of the Ajivikas did not last long. The inscriptional records inside the caves have been mutilated. This indicates that the original inhabitants were evicted by their opposing contemporaries. Basham opined that the nature of defacement point that the religious rivals of the Ajivikas wished to remove records of their inhabitation. By the time the Muslims occupied the caves, the Brahmi language became almost non- existential. Hultzsch argued that the mutilation of the inscriptions happened at the time of the installation of the Hindu images by Anantavarman (Basham, 1951).

In a recent development the Archaeological Survey of India has sought World Heritage status for the Barabar and Nagarjuni caves in Bihar. Located in Jehanabad district, these caverns are widely known as the oldest surviving rock-cut caves. Dating back to the Maurya period these caves hold immense value. The Patna circle of ASI is preparing a proposal to be sent to UNESCO for inclusion in its tentative list of the World Heritage Sites.

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